

Deliverable 9.2.4

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Abstract

In this document we report on the delivery of the Services/Virtual Machine Images to facilitate the PhenoMeNal toolsets and pipelines for the overall VRE. We report on the selection, development and deployment of the compute VMIs for all tools required in our clinical partners' data processing pipelines and highlight how we enable standardised compute capabilities within Galaxy and Jupyter.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

We have developed and containerised a set of open source tools with corresponding standardized interfaces in order to make them accessible for use in Galaxy and Jupyter workflows. We implemented exemplifying re-runnable workflows for phenomics and metabolomics for all major tool types (e.g., repository downloaders, format converters, data processing, statistics and metadata enrichment tools) and assaying technologies – namely NMR, Mass Spectrometry and Fluxomics analysis – along the requirements of our PhenoMeNal partners and clinical stakeholders. Container descriptions/VRE wrappers were generated and the tools were made available in the PhenoMeNal app library, the public PhenoMeNal Cloud Research Environment and in newly deployed VREs using the cloud portal installer. A release plan lays the path for regular stable PhenoMeNal releases.

2 PROJECT OBJECTIVES MET

The objective of delivering the basic data processing components of the scalable PhenoMeNal infrastructure for workflow generation has been reached, as has the delivery of initial data processing workflows as required by our clinical project partners. Traceability of the processing audit track and data quality is ensured by making a large fraction of the tools in the pipelines use established open data standards for input and output, and also by delivering validator containers for these formats. The general continuous integration approach is implemented via Jenkins and the whole processing workflows can be run either securely behind a local clinical firewall (bring the compute to the data) or on public cloud platforms.

Thus, we have contributed to the following objectives:

Objective 9.1 Specify and integrate software pipelines and tools utilised in the PhenoMeNal e-Infrastructure into VMIs, adhering to data standards developed in WP8 and supporting the interoperability and federation middleware developed in WP5.

Objective 9.2 Develop methods to scale-up software pipelines for high-throughput analysis, supporting execution on e.g. local clusters, private clouds, federated clouds, or GRIDs.

Moreover, the workflow developed at the National Phenome Center at ICL includes data quality control; hence, we have also contributed to:

Objective 9.3 Add **quality control** and quality assurance to pipelines to ensure high quality and reliable data, keep an **audit trail** of intermediate steps and results.

3 DETAILED REPORT OF THE DELIVERABLE

- In this document we report on the delivery of the Services-Virtual Machine Images to facilitate the PhenoMeNal toolsets and pipelines. In particular, we describe:
- The containerization and workflow-environment-specific descriptions of the tools required in the use case workflows, and inclusion into the App Library;
- Implementation of three example workflows that can be executed in this Virtual Research Environment (VRE);
- Our testing strategy at multiple levels (container, workflow, infrastructure);
- The release process for the VRE.

Containerized tools

As a major part of this deliverable we produced 42 Services Images (VMI), of which 36 are available in the App Library and will be part of the first PhenoMeNal release. Each of the individual Service VMI modules is represented by a containerized tool that is available in the PhenoMeNal App Library¹ as part of the PhenoMeNal Portal. Additionally, we have prepared Galaxy-based VRE wrappers for the containerized tools to prepare them for usage in workflows as part of our use-cases. Wrapping tools for Galaxy requires a lot of effort to coordinate common input and output structure definitions, as well as linking these to the PhenoMeNal use-cases. Where possible, we use community accepted open data standards (see WP8). To effectively manage the high number of VMIs in our project we are capturing the status of all tools in a collectively maintained spreadsheet (Fig. 1).

¹ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/app-library>

- Tool Unit testing (<https://github.com/phnmnl/phenomenal-h2020/wiki/Dockerfile-Guide#testing-features>)
- Container testing (<https://github.com/phnmnl/phenomenal-h2020/wiki/Container-testing-guides>)
- Workflow testing (<http://wft4galaxy.readthedocs.io/>)
- Infrastructure testing (<https://travis-ci.org/kubenow/KubeNow>)

Using the PhenoMeNal infrastructure for testing

In PhenoMeNal we have two deployment types of the Galaxy VRE. The “stable” deployment is being used by PhenoMeNal users and for the official PhenoMeNal Galaxy instance (<http://public.phenomenal-h2020.eu/>). The “develop” deployment is being used by PhenoMeNal developers that are creating and testing tools and Galaxy wrappers. We have documented these deployments and their purpose on the wiki³. PhenoMeNal users can deploy the stable Galaxy VRE with the graphical user interface VRE developed in WP6, whereas the “develop” type is only available to users of the “bleeding edge” version – currently mostly PhenoMeNal members. The advantage of the “develop” type is that PhenoMeNal developers can integrate and test their tools directly in the PhenoMeNal cloud infrastructure by using the latest “bleeding edge” tool versions on github or by specifying a specific local setup. If the particular testing tools include sensitive data, the testing can also be done in a private environment by creating the virtual research infrastructure locally – for instance on a laptop. The main feature of the “develop” deployment is that it contains the testing infrastructure. When testing scripts for the individual tools are supplied, our continuous integration framework, Jenkins, automatically runs them. If these scripts fail, Jenkins aborts and notifies the tool developers. This arrangement allows us to streamline development and tie it to the PhenoMeNal infrastructure to ensure continuous and sustainable software builds. More technical guidelines are available in the links specified above and under the Guidelines for Continuous Integration¹.

Format converters, preprocessing and metadata enrichment tools

Since the creation of the VMIs reported in D9.2.2, we have developed additional container VMIs to facilitate secondary data usage and to perform more metadata conversions, which are needed for the tools to be interoperable within the workflows. Table 1 contains a list of additional VMIs.

Tool name	Github repository	Workflow
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³Please refer the documents: <https://github.com/phnmnl/phenomenal-h2020/wiki/QuickStart-Installation-for-Local-PhenoMeNal-Workflow> and <https://github.com/phnmnl/phenomenal-h2020/wiki/galaxy-with-k8s>.

		available
nmrML2isa	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-nmrml2isa	✓
isatab-validator	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-isatab-validator	✓
npc2batman	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-npc2batman	✓
mtbls-dwnld	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-mtbls-dwnld	✓
mwtab2isa	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-mw2isa	
isajson-validator	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-isajson-validator	

Table 1: List of converter and I/O tools which are available as VMIs in the PhenoMeNal cloud infrastructure and are part of the first PhenoMeNal release. For some of these tools Galaxy wrappers are available on the public PhenoMeNal Galaxy instance (<http://public.phenomenal-h2020.eu>).

Mass spectrometry processing tools

Mass spectrometry data requires intensive processing. We created VMIs for the most popular mass spectrometry open source tools. As most of these tools have multiple functions and purposes, they require several wrappers that map different functionality into workflow management systems such as Galaxy. For some of these tools there are Galaxy wrappers available on the public PhenoMeNal Galaxy instance⁴. The number of mass spectrometry tools will be expanded based on our use case requirements.

Tool name	Github repository	Workflow available
metfrag-cli	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-metfrag-cli	✓
xcms	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-xcms	✓

⁴ <http://public.phenomenal-h2020.eu>

lcmsmatching	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-lcmsmatching	✓
ms-vfetc	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-ms-vfetc	✓
ipo	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-ipo	
metfamily	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-metfamily	
openms	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-openms	

Table 2: List of mass spectrometry tools which are available as VMIs in the PhenoMeNal cloud infrastructure and are part of the first PhenoMeNal release.

The Sacurine workflow

The workflow calculating the statistics in the Sacurine workflow has been adapted to use the MetaboLights download tool and was demonstrated in January within the project (Fig. 2). For the Sacurine use case, four Galaxy tools from the Workflow4Metabolomics e-infrastructure (W4M) have been containerized: **univariate** (univariate hypothesis testing), **multivariate** (OPLS multivariate modeling), **biosigner** (selection of molecular signatures for diagnostic) and **LCMS matching** (LC/MS annotation). Furthermore, a tool (**mtbls-dwnld**) was specifically developed to import data from Metabolights into Galaxy workflows. This module connects to the MetaboLights database and downloads either a full study (including raw data) or only the ISA-Tab files (thus avoiding the transfer of large volumes of unnecessary files). The tool was also designed to convert the data from ISA-Tab files into the format required by the subsequent modules in the workflow. The modules were containerized in the same way as the other four tools. The containerization and the development of code tests for the Jenkins Continuous Integration platform were straightforward. This work thus paves the way for the future containerization of the many Galaxy tools developed by the omics communities. The Sacurine use case is a sub-workflow from the W4M00001_Sacurine-statistics workflow referenced in W4M. The five modules described previously were successfully chained as a workflow, applied to the MTBLS404 data, and run on the cloud. The demonstration of a real metabolomics workflow running on the cloud is a step forward towards higher computing performance for metabolomics data analysis. This achievement was made possible by the joint work within PhenoMeNal of key European teams, including CEA and W4M (workflow and tools), EBI (MetaboLights repository of raw data; EMBASSY Cloud), and UOXF (definition of data standards).

Figure 2: Screenshot of the Sacurine workflow running in our public PhenoMeNal Galaxy instance (<http://public.phenomenal-h2020.eu>).

MetFrag workflow

MetFrag, launched in 2010, was one of the first approaches to address metabolite annotation from MS/MS spectra for hundreds of candidate structures from chemical databases by performing *in silico* fragmentation and mapping of experimental fragment peaks. Ranked candidates give hints for the molecular structure of the correct molecule for a given MS/MS spectrum.

We have implemented a workflow that imports MS/MS data from MetaboLights and pre-processes these data prior to the actual processing with the tool **metfrag-cli** (which is a command line Galaxy wrapper for MetFrag). During the design of the workflow we paid attention to rely on open data standards during the whole pipeline process of the workflow. As a consequence, we only use the mzML, mzTab and CSV data formats (Fig. 3). Currently, we are creating Galaxy wrappers to pre-process MS/MS data which has been imported from MetaboLights.

MetFrag requires access to a metabolite or small molecule structure database, like NCBI PubMed. To make MetFrag independent of this external database, it can use the containerised local PubChem mirror described in D9.2.3 “Database and backend service VMI”.

In the current development version, the workflow consists of an input node that provides an MS/MS peak list of a particular molecule – as shown in Fig. 3. These data are passed to the MetFrag-CLI node for which specific parameters are set beforehand,

including database settings, mass deviations and scoring types used to rank molecular candidates.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the MetFrag workflow running in our public PhenoMeNal Galaxy instance (<http://public.phenomenal-h2020.eu>).

NMR processing tools

NMR is an important analytical method used in many different Phenome centers and labs, including in the Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure (BBMRI). There is a growing number of open source tools and open data standards available to the NMR user community. These tools can be categorized along their basic functionalities as follows:

- Data format converters – i.e., from vendor formats to open formats (VMI: nmrmlconv)
- Data Processing, analysis and visualisation
 - I/O libraries for different programming languages (nmrglue, nmrPRO, nmrProcFlow)
 - Tools for preprocessing – e.g., SOAP-NMR, MetaboQuant, nmrProTools for Identification & quantification (Batman, rNMR, MetaboQuant)
- Statistical analysis tools (Univariate and multivariate, such as PCA)
- (Meta-)data annotation tools (ISAtools, nmrML2ISA)

These are the main tool categories occurring in NMR metabolomics and are usually found in VRE NMR data processing workflows (See Fig 4.)

Figure 4: Data processing steps and major open access tools expected within NMR based metabolomics workflows.

Table 3 provides an overview of VMIs that are already included in the PhenoMeNal cloud infrastructure. These were part of the initial selection of tools that we prepared for Galaxy workflows. The number of tools will be continuously expanded based on our use case requirements. For most of these tools Galaxy wrappers are available on the public PhenoMeNal Galaxy instance (<http://public.phenomenal-h2020.eu>).

Tool name	Github repository	Workflow available
BATMAN	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-batman	✓
metabomatching	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-metabomatching	✓
nmrmlconv	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-nmrmlconv	✓

rNMR	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-rnmr	
SOAP-NMR	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-soap-nmr	
nmrglue	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-nmrglue	
nmrpro	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-nmrpro	

Table 3: List of NMR data analysis tools which are available as VMIs in the PhenoMeNal cloud infrastructure and are part of the first PhenoMeNal release.

NPC NMR pipeline + BATMAN Workflow

We now have an early version of an NMR preprocessing pipeline, which is equivalent in functionality to the preprocessing pipeline used at the UK National Phenome Centre (NPC). Originally, the preprocessing pipeline was implemented in matlab, which is proprietary; we have now reimplemented it in an open source language (Python). In this pipeline (Figure 4) we import the NMR raw data and calculate the baseline and Peak Width (PW) with a 95% confidence level. We calibrate peaks to either glucose or lactate resonance depending on the type of sample. Currently, the input sample metadata can be either in ISA-Tab or CSV formats; the latter is generated from an in-house Lab Information Management System (LIMS) which supports both sample tracking and sample metadata storage. On the other hand, the output of the pipeline is currently a data matrix of PW values with waterpeak and baseline pass/fail, but we are also investigating the nmrML open data standard for postprocessing outputs⁵. Following the preprocessing, the output can be passed to BATMAN, an R package for the automated quantification of metabolites from NMR spectra using a Bayesian model, for which a Galaxy wrapper was created (see Fig.

⁵ i.e. posting nmrML feature requests to the nmrML Git issue tracker, e.g. <https://github.com/nmrML/nmrML/issues/169>

Figure 4: High Level Steps of the NPC's NMR Preprocessing Pipeline

Figure 5: NPC NMR pipeline and the BATMAN workflow in Galaxy

A complete workflow combining the NPC NMR data preprocessing pipeline with BATMAN post analysis is shown in Figure 5. The complete workflow runs in our PhenoMeNal Galaxy environment. As Figure 5 illustrates, the Galaxy workflow consists of 3 parts: NPC NMR pipeline, a data matrix converter and the BATMAN module.

Figure 6: NPC Preprocessing QC Report (left), NPC NMR Pipeline + BATMAN output example (right).

Along with the output dataframe produced by BATMAN, which contains data ready for uni/multivariate analysis, we also generate various detailed reports to ensure the pipeline has worked correctly. Among these is the QC summary report (see Figure 6), that contains several plots, a sample summary report, that shows the missing samples and details of samples marked for exclusion, and a final report that shows details such as the number of samples, threshold values used and other parameters settings. The reports provide evidence for users to optimise parameters, for example, to judge the suitability of preset thresholds in their configuration files. Users may need to amend or adjust parameter settings to re-run the pipeline to achieve satisfactory outcome.

Fluxomics tools

We have created a functional version of a workflow for steady-state fluxomics. The objective is the estimation of metabolic reaction-fluxes by fitting flux-balanced model predictions and experimental mass-spectrometry measurements of ¹³C propagation from labelled substrates to metabolites.

Scheme of the workflow:

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Figure 7: Overall workflow scheme for data processing in Fluxomics.

^{13}C mass-spectrometry data are contained in a CSV exchange file, which is successively transformed by the programs involved in the pipeline. The file is a matrix that contains correspondences between isotopologue abundances and signal intensities and with CDF files, together with additional descriptors. CDF files are grouped and compressed in a ZIP file.

Separate tools have been included covering complementary parts of the study of metabolic fluxes. **Ramid** is an R-tool for reading raw mass spectra contained in CDF files, which follow a standard format for RAW mass spectrometry measurements. Ramid converts raw data in signal intensities in the CSV exchange file. **Midcor** is another tool based on R. By applying midcor, uncorrected signal intensities are transformed in normalized isotopologue abundances by correcting natural isotope enrichments. Finally, corrected isotopologue abundances in the CSV exchange file are the input used for **iso2flux**, a Python based tool. This tool estimates reaction-fluxes by fitting model predictions and experimental mass-spectrometry measurements.

In addition, iso2flux requires a complete model description, including both an SBML description of all involved reaction-stoichiometries, a CSV file with the transitions in carbon positions and a CSV file with additional constraints.

Finally, three files are returned by iso2flux as outputs. Two CSV files with the description of the best fit, one with the estimated reaction fluxes, and a second file with comparisons of the measured isotopologue abundances with those predicted using the

model and the estimated flux values. A third SBML file contains confidence intervals around each estimated reaction flux, which gives a measure of the significance of the fitted fluxes. During the whole pipeline we use community accepted open data formats.

VMI containers have been created for these tools, and further, we created wrappers for them to be available in Galaxy. These tools, together with the ProteoWizard container, have been used for the creation of the workflow in Galaxy:

Figure 8: Fluxomics workflow. The corresponding tools are listed in Table 5

The number of fluxomics tools will be expanded based on our use case requirements.

Tool name	Github repository	Status
Ramid	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-ramid	Working + Workflow Available
Midcor	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-midcor	Working + Workflow Available
iso2flux	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-iso2flux	Working +

		Workflow Available
Isodyn	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-isodyn	Working + Workflow Available

Table 5: List of fluxomics tools, which are available as VMIs in the PhenoMeNal cloud infrastructure and are part of the first PhenoMeNal release. For all of these tools there are available Galaxy wrappers available on the public PhenoMeNal Galaxy instance (<http://public.phenomenal-h2020.eu>).

Post-processing and statistics tools

In metabolomics workflows, after processing the data with the domain specific tools, post-processing is required to clean up the data and to better handle noise and to carry out subsequent statistical analyses for interpretation of the results. Finally, statistical analyses create the power and the means to examine the data sets and to interpret the results in a scientific way. We have created several VMIs that perform statistical analyses on metabolomics data. These containerized tools subsume several statistical analysis that are performed on the data (e.g. univariate and multivariate are used in the **Sacurine-workflow** above).

Tool name	Github repository	Status
Univariate	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-univariate	Working + Workflow Available
Multivariate	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-multivariate	Working + Workflow Available
Biosigner	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-biosigner	Working + Workflow Available
MetaboliteIDConverter	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-MetaboliteIDConverter	Working + Workflow Available

papy	https://github.com/phnmnl/container-papy	Working
bioc_devel_metabolomics	https://github.com/phnmnl/bioc_docker	Working
bioc_devel_protmetcore	https://github.com/phnmnl/bioc_docker	Working

Table 6: List of post-processing and statistics tools, which are available as VMIs in the PhenoMeNal cloud infrastructure and are part of the first PhenoMeNal release. For most of these tools there are available Galaxy wrappers available on the public PhenoMeNal Galaxy instance (<http://public.phenomenal-h2020.eu>).

Bioconductor Metabolomics containers

The Bioconductor metabolomics Dockerfiles are maintained by PhenoMeNal members on the Bioconductor GitHub, and the images are available from Docker Hub (both stable release and current devel versions) and the PhenoMeNal container registry.

To make the huge collection of Bioconductor packages findable and accessible, a package is organised into one or more BiocViews covering Infrastructure, different BiologicalQuestions, StatisticalMethods or Technologies. Around 30 packages are listed in ResearchField Metabolomics, and almost a third of them is (co-)maintained by members of the PhenoMeNal consortium. Collectively, these packages contain most of the functionality that is required for today's metabolomics research.

In PhenoMeNal, we have included the build of the metabolomics image on our Continuous Integration (CI) Jenkins server, and work with the BioC core team to maintain this set of containers.

Release plan and process

We distinguish two types of releases being development builds and bi-annual stable releases. This distinction is necessary to balance our continuous integration methodology with the need for stable persistent referenceable versions in light of reproducible research.

Development builds, are for testing and getting access to the latest versions that PhenoMeNal has to offer. Users of our development builds provide valuable feedback that is used as input for the upcoming stable release. Development builds are provided using our continuous integration server and monitored by automated tests. These tests run on tool, container and deployment levels for optimal assessment of functionality and quality. This, however, can vary between tools and is not guaranteed. Also development

builds are not kept over a longer period and therefore should not be used in production environments.

Stable builds, on the other hand, are a selection of the tools that are considered production ready and have proven to run on the PhenoMeNal supported infrastructure (e.g. Google Cloud Platform, Amazon Web Services and local/private OpenStack installations). That means they are tested properly, are maintainable, and have been well documented. The most important aspect of a stable build is reproducibility. At any moment in time a user should be able to deploy an instance of the PhenoMeNal VRE on his/her preferred provider (or even locally for that matter), and be able to run individual tools or a complete workflow resulting in identical results (based on the same input). This we accomplish by storing all the build dependencies required by a stable release in a secure and read-only location.

Although most of the releases will be an upgrade of the previous version; it is not said that all tools in the previous version will be upgrade or even be present in the new release. Tools can be replaced or considered obsolete in upcoming versions. Most importantly will be the compatibility of tools within a release.

Release Date	Codename	Version	Supported
February 2017 (public beta)	Alanine	2017.02	+1 year
August 2017	Bucetin	2017.08	+1 year
February 2018	Cerebellin	2018.02	+1 year
August 2018	Dalcotidine	2018.08	+1 year
February 2019	Eucalyptal	2019.02	+1 year
August 2019

Table 7: Our current release schedule.

Release process

Within PhenoMeNal we have adopted a versioning strategy for containers and tools which, among other things, mandates how releases need to be performed. Here we summarize the process which leads to the release. Each container VMI is set with specific container labels, comprising the tool version and a container version. In Github, development will be done in the "develop" branch. Before each release, we merge the changes from the "develop" branch with the "master" branch. The Continuous

Integration software Jenkins will recognize the merges and will generate automatically the corresponding container for the upcoming stable release, as well as for the "bleeding edge" branch where development is continuously ongoing. Containers of the "develop" branch will be tagged with "dev_" to indicate that. Whereas all container images from the stable release are kept, only the latest versions of container images are kept in the "develop" branch. Moreover, container images are only produced when all tests (see chapter on testing above) are passed successfully. This accounts for, both, the "master" and the "develop" branch.

More technical information guidelines are available on this wiki-page: <https://github.com/phnmnl/phenomenal-h2020/wiki/Tool-container-release-process>. With this strategy, we ensure stability, longevity and sustainability of VMIs in the PhenoMeNal cloud infrastructure.

Sustainability strategy of the Compute VMIs pipeline

We currently provide 42 Compute VMIs (of which 36 will go into the first public PhenoMeNal release). The containers are the building blocks of workflows and are also the individual components which are orchestrated in our cloud infrastructure. With a 4-level testing strategy (unit testing, container testing, workflow testing and infrastructure testing; see above) we ensure that the container VMIs run without errors in our cloud infrastructure. The communication channel (the workflow graph edges) between containers (workflow nodes) is standardized via Galaxy and its content is standardized by encouraging the use of open domain data standards like mzML for mass spectrometry data.

In order to comply with the privacy guidelines, we work closely with the ELSI work package representatives, to ensure that data is secured inside the containers. In WP9 we follow two strategies: 1) Keeping data temporarily in the container VMIs until they have finished their calculations and are shut down. 2) For accessing large data sets, containers can access the 'glusterfs'-distributed file system inside the VRE. Here, data are shared temporarily to the containers within the context of glusterfs. The data transport layer is now encrypted by default. With this strategy, we ensure the maximum security of data access of the containers. With sensitive data, we recommend to use the local installation of PhenoMeNal (bringing the compute to the data). Our Compute VMIs were designed to work in such an enclosed environment. With this deliverable we create the basis to reach long-term sustainability of VMIs.

4 WORKPLAN

Utilization of resources towards this deliverable:

Partner	EMBL-EBI	ICL	IPB	UB	UOXF	SIB	UU	CEA	INRA
PM	4	3	2	4	2	2	1	2	1

5 DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE

The deliverable is submitted on time.

6 CONCLUSION

Building on Deliverables D9.2.1-D9.2.3, with D9.2.4 we now have a complete software stack to install a VRE with container orchestration, file storage, workflow engine and the discipline-specific tools to perform metabolomics research in local and public cloud infrastructures. Our release process and schedule are in place, which will allow stable releases to be (re-)deployed in the future should the need arise – for instance, to reproduce analyses or studies.

The next steps in our work will be the improvement of existing workflows for better coverage and robustness, and the preparation of additional workflows.